

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

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CONTENTS

ABOUT THE EDITORS.....	5
Welcome Speech:	
FOSTERING INNOVATION AND ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION	8
PROF. ILIA NINKA, RECTOR	
DIGITALIZATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE LABOR MARKET	9
MRS. GERTIOLA CEPANI	
ADDRESSING THE DIGITAL LEAP IN THE WESTERN BALKANS Preliminary impact exposition of the HOMO DIGITALIS Erasmus+ CBHE Project.....	10
PROF. KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS	
THE STRATEGIC ACTIONS FOR AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION	12
EMERITUS PROFESSOR, NIKOLAOS AVOURIS	
SUMMARY OF ACTIVITES	16
PART ONE: DIGITAL COMPETENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE LABOUR MARKET	19
(1) THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CASE STUDY: ALBANIAN UNIVERSITIES DURING THE PANDEMIC PERIOD	21
EMIRA SPAHAJ, EDISELA MENA, MALVINA HYSA, BLERTA AVDIA	
(2) BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES IN ALBANIAN HIGHER EDUCATION FOR STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES. A MIXED-METHODS ANALYSIS.....	37
BLERTA DRENOFCI (ÇANI), VALBONA NATHANAILI	
(3) THE DIGITAL EMPLOYMENT GAP IN ALBANIA Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	61
GERTJANA HASALLA	
PART TWO: INSTITUTIONAL STRATEGIES AND POLICY DEVELOPMENT.....	75
(4) INTEGRATED TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT AND RESTORATION STRATEGY FOR THE ‘TOPULLI’ HOUSE Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	77
NIKOLLA VESHO, PANAGIOTIS KYRATISIS, AJLA GJOKA, LUMTURI HASKA, SARA CIBA, MIGENA GJONI, ARDIS DUKA, ROMIR MAZARI	

(5)	THE ROLE OF MOOCS AND OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	101
	DORINA MINXURI	
(6)	LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGIES AND DIGITAL HUMANITIES FOR LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES AND COMMUNITIES.....	113
	ARBANA KADRIU, LEJLA ABAZI-BEXHETI	
(7)	THE COGNITIVE-DIGITAL TURN IN HIGHER EDUCATION A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio.....	125
	FULVIO PAPADHOPULLI, MEGI TAF AJ	
(8)	DEFINING A STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN FOR AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	141
	NIKOLAOS AVOURIS	
(9)	INSTITUTIONAL POLICIES AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	153
	HAJDIN BERISHA, AGRON HAJDARI, BEKIM SAMADRAXHA	
PART THREE: THE INTENDED AND ATTAINED CURRICULUM.....		155
(10)	DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN SOCIAL SCIENCES – A PILOT STUDY From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project	157
	VALBONA NATHANAILI, BLERTA DRENOFCI (ÇANI), KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUKIS, DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ, ARBANA KADRIU, ANISA DUKA	
(11)	ENHANCING LEARNING THROUGH MULTIMEDIA CULTURAL HERITAGE APPLICATIONS Managing Cognitive Load.....	177
	MERIMA MUSLIĆ, DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ, VENSADA OKANOVIĆ, SELMA RIZVIĆ	
(12)	INTEGRATING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES INTO HIGHER EDUCATION CURRICULA A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the HOMO DIGITALIS Project	193
	JUNA MUÇA, ANXHELA LASKA, ELPINIQI MERKURI, EDVALDO BEGOTARAJ	
CONFERENCE SUMMARY AND REFLECTIONS.....		209
	VALBONA NATHANAILI	
INDEX OF AUTHORS AND PAPER NUMBERS		211

VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafli has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

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SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

INSTITUTIONAL POLICIES AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The rapid evolution of digital technologies is reshaping the landscape of higher education and demanding institutions to align their policies and practices with the skills required for a knowledge-based economy. Within the Kosovo higher education system, fostering digital competencies has emerged as a strategic priority to enhance teaching, learning, research, and graduate employability. This paper explores how institutional policies, and strategic directions can drive the systematic development of digital skills in higher education. It examines the current policy frameworks, highlights key challenges and identifies opportunities for further advancement. The study emphasizes the need for coherent governance, inclusive digital transformation, and sustainable investment to ensure higher education institutions can adapt to technology trends. Ultimately, the paper argues that advancing digital competencies is not only a technological imperative but also a strategic enabler for quality, equity, and international competitiveness in Kosovo's higher education system.

Keywords: Higher education, technology, policies, strategy.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

HAJDIN BERISHA

Hajdin Berisha completed his BBA and MBA in Kuala Lumpur and received his Ph.D. from University of Marmara in Istanbul. Currently he teaches at the Public International Business College Mitrovica in Kosovo. His research interests and expertise include both management and education. Much of his work has been on improving organisational structures, corporate strategy, and corporate governance.

AGRON HAJDARI

Dr. Agron Hajdari is an Assistant Professor at the Faculty of International Business Management and a member of the Steering Council at the Public International Business College in Mitrovica (IBCM), Kosovo. He lectures in the fields of business, management, and entrepreneurship. With over 20 years of professional experience, Dr. Hajdari has made significant contributions to Kosovo's education system, particularly in education policy reform, vocational education and training, higher education, and the alignment of education with labour market needs. He has served in various expert roles, including project manager, capacity-building advisor, and quality assurance manager, and has been engaged in numerous international donor-funded initiatives supporting youth, employment, and education. His professional portfolio includes project development and management, institutional strengthening, and policy advising. Dr. Hajdari's research interests focus on entrepreneurship, particularly returnee entrepreneurship, return migration, labour market integration, and management. He is actively involved in both academic and applied research initiatives.

BEKIM SAMADRAXHA

Bekim Samadraxha, completed his BBA and MBA at the University of Prishtina and obtained his Ph.D. from the Public University of Tirana in Albania. He currently works in the Higher Education Department at the Ministry of Education, Science, Technology, and Innovation in Kosovo. His research interests are focused on legislation and the higher education strategy to improve the quality of higher education. He has also a long experience in teaching at several higher education institutions and has led the Kosovo Accreditation Agency.

INDEX OF AUTHORS AND PAPER NUMBERS

Abazi-Bexheti, Lejla, 6
Avdia, Blerta, 1
Avouris, Nikolaos, 8
Begotaraj, Edvaldo, 12
Berisha, Hajdin, 9
Bošković, Dušanka, 10, 11
Ciba, Sara, 4
Drenofci (Çani), Blerta, 2, 10
Duka, Anisa, 10
Duka, Ardis, 4
Giakoumis, Konstantinos, 10
Gjoka, Ajla, 4
Gjoni, Migena, 4
Hajdari, Agron, 9
Hasalla, Gertjana, 3
Haska, Lumturi, 4
Hysa, Malvina, 1
Kadriu, Arbana, 6, 10
Kyriatsis, Panagiotis, 4
Laska, Anxhela, 12
Mazari, Romir, 4
Mena, Edisela, 1
Merkuri, Elpiniqi, 12
Minxuri, Dorina, 5
Muça, Juna, 12
Muslić, Merima, 10
Nathanaili, Valbona, 2, 10
Okanović, Vensada, 10
Papadhopulli, Fulvio, 7
Rizvić, Selma, 10
Samadraxha, Bekim, 9
Spahaj, Emira, 1
Tafaj, Megi, 7
Vesho, Nikolla, 4

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

PROF. ILIA NINKA

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education is about more than technology. It is about developing university-level strategies and adequate national and regional policies to support digital transformation. Albanian Higher Education Institutions have not yet developed an ethical framework for the use of ChatGPT and similar AI applications.

DR. VALBONA NATHANAILI

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

DR. KETI HOXHA

Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

PROF. DUŠANKA BOŠKović

... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

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